

School of Education Alumni's Testimonials Posted via Social Media: A Tracer Documentation in the SED's Facebook Page

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ABSTRACT

The study showcased the School of Education (SED) alumni's testimonials on their feedback about San Isidro College, their Alma Mater via the SED's Facebook page launched in 2021. The descriptive research design employing a questionnaire via the Google form was sent to the alumni in the group chat of the School of Education graduates. The questionnaire asked on the profile of the alumni, the feedback with the indicators and other information. Frequency and percentage were used to analyze the results of the study. Results indicated that the posting of the SED Alumni's testimonials via the SED's Facebook page was positively responded by a 100% of the participants. Their testimonials promote the Teacher Education program to target enrollees. Their feedback featured the experiences at San Isidro College on how their goals were achieved and how their lives were transformed for the better as they earned the degree and succeeded in the practice of their profession. They acknowledged the initiative of the school that the alumni can reconnect with their Alma Mater. The use of the Social Media for the testimonials is effective especially that a lot of the young people browse the internet for information influencing their decision making. San Isidro College, School of Education has to strengthen its gathering of testimonials and explore more venues to showcase more alumni testimonials in varied platforms where the potential enrollees are more drawn to use now.

Subject Area

Teaching

Keywords: *Testimonials, Feedback, Social Media*

INTRODUCTION

Marketing plays an important role in the promotion of goods and services among the target clients and consumers. With this, testimonials are among the crucial ways to establish and build the trust that can be drawn from the potential clients and customers to patronize the service like that of an academe which offers different programs. The social media via the Facebook is one vehicle for people to have their experiences posted and viewed by the social media users.

As cited by Shelly Walsh (2022) in her article entitled *Top 10 Social Media Sites and platforms*, around 58.7 % of the global population use the social media as one of the sources of information. According to Chris Hazell (2022), using testimonials in Higher Education Marketing is putting and *elevating the school's brand in the minds of the audience using a tested and easier framework to follow*. It puts the school at the center of the brand's story.

The Higher Education Marketing (2023) of a school is an outlet to share and help others through trustworthy testimonials or what others have positively experienced from the school or college. However, it is a challenge to really track down those with experience of the school's services which include committed faculty members, alumni, donors, and other stakeholders. Tips to success in Testimonials included (1) build testimonial surveys for each audience (2) Go where the audience is, (3) Think through how to utilize each type of testimonial, (4) Video testimonials are powerful, (5) get creative when displaying testimonials and (6) long form testimonials can be powerful (abound college, 2022).

According to the International Consultants for Education and Fairs (ICEF, 2013) student's testimonials will provide the experience that students want and help them achieve their goals. In this way, the strengths and benefits of the academic programs of the school or college are reinforced as a considerable educational investment of time and resources. It is likely possible that there is that movement toward the student being convinced to enroll in a particular school or college. Multiple narratives or testimonials are integral to the overall marketing effort.

Featured alumni testimonials on the other hand provides an opportunity for prospective students to connect directly to individual alumni on aspects how the lives of the alumni changed and how they have achieved their goals in life. Planning out on the production and distribution of the testimonials whether written or video testimonials play an important role in the dissemination of the information about the program, the school, the location and some insights like what made the school standout and why the alumni chose the school.

ICEF added credibility and authenticity of the message are important functions of testimonials. There must be a balance of the desire to feature fairly articulate and successful students or alumni. Video and written testimonials should have compelling content, with specific rather than general terms on how the program helped to achieve their goals. The testimonials not only highlight the benefits of the chosen program but also gets a sense of students' or alumni's personal lives and challenges.

According to Noetic Marketer (2022) the respected alumni can have testimonials that can give prospective students with great insights into their experiences, programs and possible career options after earning a degree. In this way, the current students can reach out or network with

alumni and create strong connections. Alumni Testimonials are very important for higher education.

Thus, the School of Education of San Isidro College posted the SED alumni's testimonials with their success stories via the SED's Facebook page. This is an inspiring initiative that the School of Education believes will contribute to increase and sustain the SED's presence in the social media and eventually increase the enrollees in the Teacher Education Programs - Bachelor of Secondary majors in English, Filipino, Mathematics, and Values Education and Bachelor of Elementary Education.

This study also traced the SED alumni who have succeeded in their chosen program and become productive in their careers in the formation and education of the young in the community.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored in the Higher Education Marketing (Hazell, 2021) in showcasing testimonials and why it matters in social media for Schools. Testimonials with information on the kind of students at an institution, the types of careers they pursue and how the school helped them in their path is crucial for the correct or appropriate match that will eventually turn prospects into enrolled students.

Testimonials are all about storytelling that allows the school to share the students' unique and general paths which improve the "trustworthiness factor" of the school as prospective enrollees have access to real feedback from those who were once in the position as students. Testimonials are influential and powerful in the student recruitment process. Optimizing the school's digital and social media presence gets prospective students to notice the experience of the alumni that helped them succeed, videos for instance have great impact among the audience (Hazell, 2021).

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram on the framework of the study. The figure shows two boxes with the independent variable, SED Alumni's Testimonials posted on the Facebook page of the SED with the arrow connected to the next box that is the dependent variable, the target increase of the SED enrollees in the Teacher Education Programs of San Isidro College, namely BSE Major in English, Filipino, Mathematics and Values Education and BEEd.

Figure 1.
Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study showcased the testimonial feedback of the School of Education (SED) alumni posted via SED Facebook page during the Academic Year 2021-2022.

Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the SED alumni who submitted their testimonials to be posted at the SED fb page, considering:
 - 1.1 gender;
 - 1.2 age;
 - 1.3 program taken;
 - 1.4 year graduated;
 - 1.5 current job;
 - 1.6 designation; and
 - 1.7 school/agency/company affiliation?
2. What is/ are the most dominant SED Alumni's Testimonials posted via SED's fb page?
3. What are the reasons that motivate the alumni to participate in the submission of them testimonials for posting at the SED's Facebook page?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Twenty-five alumni of the School of Education in San Isidro College participated in this study. San Isidro College is a higher Education institution of learning situated in Impalambong, Malaybalay City. It is the only Catholic Higher Education institution in Malaybalay City offering the degree programs in Arts and Sciences, Education, Nursing, Accountancy, Business Management, Office Administration, Engineering, and Information Technology.

This study utilized the descriptive research design. The data were gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire divided in three parts. This questionnaire was sent in the group chat of the School of Education Graduates via google form. The study used frequency and percentage to analyze the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the respondents

There were twenty-five alumni from the School of Education who took part in the study. Their testimonials were posted on the Facebook page of the School of Education (SED) on October 5, 2021, World Teachers' Day as the highlight of the Education Week 2021 celebration. A survey questionnaire via the Google form asked the SED alumni about their profile, their dominant feedback on the posted SED alumni testimonials and the reasons that motivate them to participate in submitting their testimonials.

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. The result shows that majority of the respondents are female comprising the sixty percent (60%) of the graduates who responded to the call of the School of Education to give their testimony on their learning experiences during their studies at San Isidro College, while the male respondents consist of forty percent (40%). Generally, there were more female students at San Isidro College hence this result is evidently showing this phenomenon.

Table 1.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Gender

GENDER	<i>f</i>	%
Male	10	40
Female	15	60
TOTAL	25	100

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. The result shows that majority of the respondents belong to the age bracket between 21-31 years old. This means that most of them are young and still new in the field of teaching, while eight (8%) percent are those in the age bracket of 53 years old or older. This finding is expected especially that the younger graduates are more exposed to the social media even while they were schooling at San Isidro College. They belong to the generation of new technologies and they could easily respond to the social media postings.

Table 2.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Age

AGE BRACKET	<i>f</i>	%
21-31 years old	9	36
32-42 years old	7	28
43-53 years old	7	28
53 years old or older	2	8
TOTAL	25	100

Table 3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms course/program taken when they were studying at San Isidro College. The result shows that the BSE-Religious Education Program got the highest percentage of graduates which is equal to thirty-six percent (36%) and the rest of the courses who responded in this research is lower than the percentage of the majority.

Table 3.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Course/Program

COURSE/PROGRAM	<i>f</i>	%
BEED	6	24
BSE-English	6	24
BSE-Mathematics	4	16
BSE-Religious Education/Values Education	9	36
TOTAL	25	100

Table 4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of year the alumni graduated from San Isidro College. The result shows sixteen percent (16%) of the respondents graduated in 2013. The rest of the respondents graduated from the year 1973 up to 2020, and the number of these graduates is very minimal compared to 2009, 2013 and 2018.

Table 4.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Year Graduated

YEAR GRADUATED	<i>f</i>	%
1973	1	4
1987	1	4
1994	1	4
1995	2	8
1997	2	8
1998	1	4
2001	1	4
2009	3	12
2010	2	8
2013	4	16
2017	1	4
2018	3	12
2019	2	8
2020	1	4
TOTAL	25	100

Table 5 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their previous job. The result shows that sixty percent (60%) of the respondents says not applicable or no job at all while some are high school principal, into teaching, assistant coordinator and call center agent as their previous job. This finding indicates that the most of the graduates have their first teaching jobs as teachers and not in other fields.

Table 5.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Previous Job

PREVIOUS JOB	<i>f</i>	%
N/A	15	60
High School Principal	1	4
Teaching	7	28
Asst. Coordinator	1	4
Call Center Agent	1	4
TOTAL	25	100

Table 6 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of current job. The result shows that seventy-six percent (76%) of the respondents are into teaching as their current job. The rest of the respondents who are teacher education graduates land into different jobs like Church Worker, Marketing Officer, Hemodialysis Technician, School Leader and one was a Graduate Student. The finding implies that the graduates really practiced the profession that they were trained for. They really applied their course in the jobs that they are currently in.

Table 6.

Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Current Job

CURRENT JOB	<i>f</i>	%
Teaching	19	76
Church Worker	1	4
Marketing Officer	1	4
Hemodialysis Technician	1	4
School Leader	1	4
Graduate Studies	1	4
N/A	1	4
TOTAL	25	100

Table 7 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of designation. The result shows that twenty-four percent (24%) of the respondents are having a designation as Teacher 1 in the Department of Education. The rest of the respondents have varied designations like Christian Living Teacher, Religious Coordinator, Marketing Officer, Secondary Principal, Hemodialysis Technician II, Senior High School Coordinator, Senior High School Teacher and Dean of Student Affairs. The result reveals that twelve out of twenty-five respondents are teacher practitioners. Since the participants belong to the younger group, it is expected that their designations would fall in the Teacher 1 to 3 bracket.

Table 7.

Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Designation

DESIGNATION	<i>f</i>	%
Teacher 1	6	24
Teacher 2	2	8
Teacher 3	4	16
Christian Living Teacher	2	8
Religious Coordinator	1	4
Marketing Officer	1	4
Secondary Principal	3	12
Hemodialysis Technician II	1	4
Senior High School Coordinator	1	4
Senior High School Teacher	1	4
Dean of Student Affairs	1	4
TOTAL	25	100

Table 8 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the agency or sector they are connected with. The result shows that fifty-two percent (52%) are now connected in the government particularly, in the Department of Education. Forty-four percent (44%) of the respondents are working in some of the private entities or institutions here and abroad.

Table 8.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of Agency

AGENCY	<i>f</i>	%
Public	13	52
Private	11	44
N/A	1	4
TOTAL	25	100

Table 9 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of school or company address. The result reveals that ninety-two percent (92%) of the respondents are working in a company or agency that is located locally or within the province they are residing. The eight percent (8%) of the respondents are now connected to a company or agency located abroad.

Table 9.
Demographic Profile of the respondent in terms of School/Company Address

AGENCY	<i>f</i>	%
Local	23	92
Abroad	2	8
TOTAL	25	100

Alumni's Testimonials on their experiences at San Isidro College posted at SED's Facebook Page

Table 10 presents the feedback on the Alumni's testimonials posted on the SED's Facebook Page. The results shows that one hundred percent (100%) of the respondents say yes to the survey of the School of Education regarding the posting of the Alumni's testimonials in the SED Facebook page. This implies the initiative that was done by the School of Education generated a positive response among the Teacher Education Graduates of San Isidro College. It further demonstrates that the graduates are happy to share their success stories and how the school was able to mold them into what they are today.

Table 10.

Alumni's Feedback on the Testimonials about their Experiences at San Isidro College posted at SED's Facebook Page

CRITERIA	YES		NO	
	f	%	f	%
1. A letter of request for the Alumni's Testimonials was sent through my messenger or e-mail.	25	100	0	0
2. The lay-out of the Alumni's Testimonials both in video and written formats was appropriate.	25	100	0	0
3. The request for the Alumni's Testimonials ignites interest, inspiration and cooperation.	25	100	0	0
4. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials at the SED's Facebook page informs and guides the target enrollees of the Teacher Education Program.	25	100	0	0
5. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials provides the quality and values experienced at SIC, School of Education.	25	100	0	0
6. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials builds credibility and instill trust at San Isidro College, School of Education.	25	100	0	0
7. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials is a helpful "marketing" effort of San Isidro College, School of Education.	25	100	0	0
8. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials helps establish top promoters of the Teacher Education Program at San Isidro College.	25	100	0	0
9. The posting of the Alumni's help provides the data on the employability of SED graduates.	25	100	0	0
10. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials has its impact on teaching as a profession and as a vocation.	25	100	0	0
11. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials in the video format is engaging.	25	100	0	0
12. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials in the written format is effective.	25	100	0	0
13. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials has to be sustained.	25	100	0	0
14. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials helps establish the linkage of San Isidro College, School of Education.	25	100	0	0
15. The posting of the Alumni's Testimonials helps sustain a positive, authentic and top-of-mind awareness of the formation of San Isidro College, School of Education.	25	100	0	0

The testimonials of the Teacher Education graduates encourage potential students who are pursuing higher education, they are making the most crucial decision of their future careers. Many different aspects like choosing a city, school, and program may affect their ultimate decision.

For undergraduates, student life is very important; the atmosphere, campus and social life are major selling points. For graduate students, specific programs and networking opportunities become the main focus to enhance their careers.

To encourage students to consider an institution, it can highlight many things across its website and through some platforms, which can present the school values, what the school's offer, and

more. However, what truly creates a more profound connection is when potential students learn about a school directly from the original source through *testimonials*.

Testimonials for higher education allow students to learn about current or past students' experiences and get a more direct telling of the atmosphere, what to expect, and what campus life is like. More importantly, it allows graduate students to develop a deeper connection and build trust with faculty while getting more feedback on program expectations and outcomes (Noetic Marketer, 2022)

Reasons why the SED Alumni give their testimonials of their experiences at San Isidro College

There are significant reasons that motivated the SED alumni to give their testimonials on their experiences at San Isidro College while they were still a student in the institution. Table 11 summarizes the results of what they say.

Table 11.

Significant reasons of the alumni to have the testimonials on their experiences at San Isidro College posted on the SED fb page

REASON	<i>f</i>	%
to respond to the request	24	96%
to express gratitude to SIC and SED	19	76%
to share success story	18	72%
to inspire future enrollees	17	68%
to influence enrollees to choose SIC, SED	18	72%
to reconnect with the Alma Mater	17	68%

There are additional comments given by the alumni aside from the significant reasons that they posted. These include: congratulatory messages; contribution to SIC's promotion of the SED's program; boost confidence and esteem of Isidrans; good initiative of SIC to sustain; amazing activity with pride and impact; and ignite gratitude to the Alma Mater.

SUMMARY

This study showcased the testimonials of the School of Education's Alumni and their views on the posting of testimonials via the Facebook page of the School of Education. The study revealed there were more female participants than the male alumni participants. Thirty-six percent of the participants belong to the age bracket between 21-23 years old. Most participants in the study were graduates of BSE-Religions Education Major. Majority of the participants were from Batch 2013. The greater bulk of the alumni were in the teaching practice, mostly having the rank of Teacher I in the Department of Education.

On the views of the Alumni in the posting of their testimonials via the Facebook page of the SED, the alumni's feedback was 100% positive in the fifteen indicators. They responded with commendable comments, e.g., being an alumni of San Isidro College boost their confidence and their pride as Isidrans. They recognized the relevance and the impact that San Isidro College has given their lives and their profession. They recognized the impacts of the core values that San Isidro College foster.

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Furthermore, the reasons and comments of the alumni on the posting of their testimonials via the Facebook page of the SED highlighted the alumni's appreciation, gratitude and a way to reconnect with their Alma Mater.

CONCLUSION

The posting of the SED Alumni's testimonials via the SED's Facebook page was found helpful in the promotion of the Teacher Education program of San Isidro College. The posting of the SED Alumni's testimonials provided the target audience or enrollees the experiences of the graduates at San Isidro College that helped them in achieving their goals and become professional teachers in the field. The testimonials' format via video and written feedback were positively responded as engaging and effective.

The posting of the testimonials of the SED alumni via the SED's Facebook page provided the opportunity to give feedback on the positive, engaging and compelling stories of the alumni in their pursuit of the Teacher Education degree at San Isidro College and how their lives have been transformed with it. The alumni's real-life experiences as students of the institution, then graduated with the degree and practiced their profession, served as a winning edge to convince potential students to enroll in the program.

RECOMMENDATIONS

San Isidro College, School of Education needs to sustain the posting of the testimonials of the success stories of the SED alumni. Aside from the written and video formats, the SED needs to strengthen its gathering of testimonials with a focal person to take charge of this type of marketing for the Teacher Education program, to have potential enrollees who will excel in the program, and most likely to succeed in the Teaching Profession or career. The School of Education can explore more venues to consistently and constantly feature the success stories of more alumni in varied platforms. Their stories are inspiring and motivating, hence these could be good marketing strategies for future educators.

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